

Controlling sheath rot (ShR) in rice

H.D. Lewin and P. Vidhyasekaran, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai 612101, India

All the high yielding cultivars in Tamil Nadu are susceptible to ShR caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* Sawada. The disease is severe during samba and thaladi seasons (Aug-Feb).

Several fungicides inhibited mycelial growth of the fungus *in vitro*. Their efficacy in the field was tested with cultivar Co 43 in four annual trials 1982-86. Plot size was 24 m² in a randomized block design with 4 replications. The fungicides were sprayed at panicle initiation and 15 d later. Disease intensity was assessed 10 d before harvest.

All fungicides tested — carbendazim (0.1%), edifenphos (0.1%), mancozeb (0.25%), thiophanate methyl (0.1%), captafol (0.125%), carboxin (0.2%), glycofene (0.2%), validamycin (0.1%), IBP (0.1%), iprodione (0.1%), tridemorph (0.1%), and copper oxychloride (0.25%) — were ineffective. □

Pseudomonas fluorescens suppresses development of bacterial blight (BB) symptoms

C.S. Anuratha and S.S. Gnanamanickam, Centre for Advanced Studies in Botany, Guindy, University of Madras, Madras 600025, India

Xanthomonas campestris pv. *oryzae*, the BB pathogen, was isolated from naturally infected IR20 and ADT36 plants collected from Coimbatore and Tirurkuppam fields. We also isolated native strains of *P. fluorescens* (biotype III) from roots of rice, pearl millet, and citrus.

In *in vitro* assays, all *P. fluorescens* strains restricted the growth of *X. c.* pv. *oryzae*. The strain isolated from rice inhibited growth the most. The diameter of inhibition zones varied

from 1.1 to 5.1 cm. The citrus strain was used in greenhouse experiments. Bacteria-coated rice seeds and nontreated seeds were planted in pots.

P. fluorescens (10⁸ cfu/ml) was mixed with a 1% solution of sterile carboxy methyl cellulose and powdered vermiculite, and dried overnight at room temperature (28°C). Control seeds were coated with a mixture that did not contain the bacteria. Bacterized seedlings received a spray with *P. fluorescens* (10⁸ cfu/ml) 20 d after seeding. Four hours later, bacterized and nonbacterized seedlings were inoculated with *X. c.* pv. *oryzae* (10⁶ cfu/ml) by the standard clipping technique. The seedlings were maintained on greenhouse benches (24-25 °C). Severity of BB was recorded 7 d after inoculation.

Bacterized rice plants showed substantial reduction (40-60%) in BB severity (see table). □

Effect of *Pseudomonas fluorescens* treatment on BB incidence in rice, Madras, India.^a

Cultivar	Treatment	BB index ^b in 3 experiments		
		I	II	III
TN1	Untreated	3.6	5.6	6.3
	Treated	1.9	3.0	3.8
	Difference	1.7**	2.6**	2.5**
IR8	Untreated	3.4	7.2	—
	Treated	2.0	3.3	—
	Difference	1.4*	3.9**	—
TKM9	Untreated	1.6	—	—
	Treated	3.0	—	—
	Difference	4.6**	—	—

^aAv of 60-187 observations each. ^b't' value significant at P = 0.05 (*) and P = 0.01 (**).

Multiplication and movement of bacterial blight (BB) pathogen in the rice plant

P.R. Ray and J.N. Chand, Plant Pathology Department, HAU, Hisar, India; and S. S. Malik, HAU, Rice Research Station, Kaul 132021, India

Multiplication of the BB pathogen in host tissue would be reflected in the total inoculum generated and scope for further disease buildup and spread.

Seed of resistant IET4141 and susceptible TN1 were sown separately in earthen pots during Jul-Aug 1985. Seedlings were thinned to five uniformly spaced plants per pot.

Plants were inoculated at 6 wk with bacterial suspension (OD 1 at 600 nm) using the clipping technique. Lesion lengths were measured in 10 leaves of each variety at 3, 6, 9, 12, and 15 d after inoculation.

One-square-centimeter sample leaf areas from the tip of inoculated leaves collected at intervals up to 12 d were assessed for *in vivo* multiplication. Each leaf piece was macerated aseptically in a mortar and pestle and a tenfold dilution was plated on NDA in triplicated petri plates. The petri plates were incubated at 27-30°C and colonies were counted after 48 h. Two leaf pieces were used for each variety at each interval.

The *in vivo* multiplication of the bacterium and population buildup per unit area of inoculated leaves at different intervals were faster in the susceptible variety than in the resistant variety (see table). Lesions developed in the susceptible variety when the population level reached 10³ at 3 d and expanded rapidly to a maximum of 15 cm at 15 d. In the resistant variety, lesions developed at 9 d after inoculation when the population level reached about 10⁶ and expanded gradually to a maximum of 3.5 cm at 15 d. The bacterium population declined faster in the lesions of the susceptible variety than in the resistant variety. Most of the lesion area in both

varieties became necrotic after 12 d.

The rate of multiplication was consistently higher in the susceptible than in the resistant variety. It appeared that lesion size was not necessarily determined by the population of the pathogen but by a particular host-pathogen relationship. □

Multiplication and development of lesions caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* in diseased rice plants, India.

Days after inoculation	Bacterial cells/cm ² leaf area		Nature and range of lesion length (cm)	
	TN1	ET4141	TN1	IET4141
3	2.83 × 10 ³	1.0 × 10 ³	0.2-0.5, grey green	No lesion
6	2.65 × 10 ⁵	1.5 × 10 ⁴	0.5-1.5, yellow	No lesion
9	2.16 × 10 ³	1.5 × 10 ⁶	2.0-5.0, yellow	0.5-0.8, light yellow
12	2.65 × 10 ⁶	1.33 × 10 ⁵	5.0-10.0, brownish	1.0-1.5, yellow
15	Necrotic lesion	Necrotic lesion	7.0-15.0, straw color	1.5-3.5, brownish

Occurrence of rice ragged stunt virus (RSV) in Sri Lanka

K. W. Jayasena, Regional Research Station, Angunukolapalana, Sri Lanka; and H. Hibino, IRRI, Philippines

Plants showing symptoms similar to those of rice RSV were first observed in Hambantota district in 1984. Varieties BG276-5, BG34-8, BG94-1,

BG34-6, and BG380 were affected. Disease incidence ranged from 20 to 70% in farmers' fields in Weeraketiya and Ranna.

Plants with typical symptoms collected from Weeraketiya, Walasmulla, Belliatta, Ranna, and Jandura were tested for virus recovery. Virus-free *Nilaparvata lugens* and *Nephotettix* sp. reared on TN1 plants in insect-proof cages were allowed to

feed on infected plants for 4 d, then confined with 7-d-old TN1 seedlings for 4 d.

The first symptoms similar to those reported for RSV were observed 21 d after inoculation. *N. lugens* but not *Nephotettix* sp. transmitted the disease to TN1 seedlings. Dried infected TN1 leaves were serologically tested at IRRI. ELISA test confirmed RSV in extracts of the leaves. □

Pest Control and Management
INSECTS

Meadow grasshopper
***Conocephalus longipennis* damage to rice spikelets**

A. T. Barrion and J. A. Litsinger, Entomology Department, IRRI

Tettigoniids as foliage feeders occur on rice worldwide. The nocturnal *C. longipennis* (de Haan) is more abundant in crops past the vegetative stage.

It shows dual food habits - as a pest feeding on rice foliage and as a predator of rice bug and stem borer eggs and nymphs of leafhoppers and planthoppers. *Conocephalus* also eats the highly nutritive rice anthers by cutting through the lemma or palea. In the process, it damages rice spikelets.

Whitish cut holes on damaged 1-d-old spikelets become noticeable when they turn brown on the third day (see figure). We found that caged adults can destroy 10-28 spikelets daily.

Conocephalus damage can be distinguished from bird, rat, or rice bug damage because only small holes

Conocephalus damage to rice spikelets: undamaged (left), 1-d-old damage (middle), and 3-d-old damage (right).

are eaten in each spikelet. Feeding birds and rats strip off many spikelets.

Bugs feeding on seeds do not make noticeable holes in spikelets. □